

**FOLLOW TESSERA
ON ITS ONLINE WORLD**

TESSERA **AT A GLANCE**

TESSERA aims to conduct the preparatory work for the creation of high-quality large-scale trusted and shareable datasets supporting the European Security Data Space for Innovation.

Project Details

GA Number: 101145802

Start Date: March 2024

Duration: 24 months

Call: ISF-2022-TFI-AG-DATA

Project coordinator: CERTH

CONSORTIUM

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TESSERA

**TOWARDS THE DATASETS FOR THE EUROPEAN
SECURITY DATA SPACE FOR INNOVATION**

Co-funded by
the European Union

AMBITION

TESSERA conducts the preparatory work for the creation of high-quality, large-scale, trusted, and shareable datasets to support the European Security Data Space for Innovation (EU SDSI).

Focus will be given on defining the requirements for the interoperability and shareability of heterogeneous datasets, considering their compliance to privacy and fundamental human rights, as well as on specifying the architecture of the data-related national components of EU SDSI.

TESSERA builds upon and complements past and ongoing relevant initiatives and fosters the engagement of interested stakeholders, including EU agencies and associations, Law Enforcement, and industry.

OBJECTIVES

Explore the landscape of datasets in the field of security

Define requirements for data quality assessment tools in the field of security

Design the low-level architecture of the data-related national components for the European Security Data Space.

Engage stakeholders in the field of security and organise technical workshops to exchange best practices and lessons learnt

Produce a report with the main achievements, results, and outcomes of the project activities

IMPACT

Short-term

Identify the conditions for the creation, availability, interoperability, accessibility, and shareability of high quality trusted datasets and data models, appropriate for training, testing, and validating data-driven AI systems

Long-term

Foster the adoption of standards and AI technologies to enable data reuse across EU Member States and facilitate Law Enforcement in tackling modern challenges in their fight against crime.